

Controlling Type I Error Rates for Secondary Endpoints through an Alpha Spending Method

Biju (Ryan) Wang¹, Eunyoung Suh¹, Steven Sun¹
Wentao Lu¹

¹Johnson & Johnson Innovative Medicine, 920 US-202, Raritan, NJ 08869

Abstract

At the interim analysis (IA) of a study, if superiority of the investigational product (IP) over the control on the primary efficacy endpoint is established, superiority of IP over the control on secondary efficacy endpoints will be tested sequentially at the significance level corresponding to the O'Brien-Fleming boundary using the information fraction (IF) of 60%. However, the true IF value for a specific secondary efficacy endpoint depends on the final number of that endpoint event collected at the end of study, which is unknown at the time of IA. We propose to adjust the alpha level at the final analysis to control the overall type I error rate in testing for secondary efficacy endpoints. A simulation study demonstrates that the proposed alpha spending method is expected to effectively control the type I error rates for secondary efficacy endpoints. It also shows that the differences between true IF values and the benchmark value of 60% for secondary efficacy endpoints are limited regardless of treatment effect sizes, which can be attributed to the similarity in risk over time patterns.

Keywords: Overall type I error control; alpha spending method; interim analysis; information fraction

1. Introduction

In clinical trials evaluating treatments for cardiovascular (CV) risk reduction, establishing the superiority of an investigational product (IP) over control is one type of the primary objectives. Typically, the primary efficacy endpoint is chosen as the time to the first occurrence of a specific CV event up to global targeted endpoint date (GTED). The hazard ratio (HR) comparing the IP to control serves as the key population-level summary measure, quantifying the treatment effect on CV risk reduction.

When the trial demonstrates superiority of the IP over control on the primary efficacy endpoint either at interim analysis (IA) or final analysis (FA), it often proceeds to evaluate secondary efficacy endpoints. These secondary analyses provide additional insights into the treatment's broader effects, but they also pose a statistical challenge: how to appropriately control the overall type I error rate to avoid inflation for multiple tests at IA and FA for a secondary efficacy endpoint ([Ciolino, Kaizer, & Bonner, 2023](#)).

For the primary efficacy endpoint, IA happens when the information fraction (IF), which indicates the proportion of total information (e.g., number of events) collected at the interim analysis relative to the planned total ([DeMets & Lan, 1994](#)), is 60% as an example and the IF value can be well controlled as the number of primary efficacy events are pre-specified. The overall type I error rate for the primary efficacy endpoint at IA and FA is controlled based on the O'Brien-Fleming (OBF) boundary ([O'Brien & Fleming, 1979](#)) ($Z = -2.67$, 2-sided IA, $\alpha = 0.0076$; $Z = -1.98$, 2-sided FA, $\alpha = 0.0476$). The same strategy also applies to the secondary efficacy endpoints at plan phase. However, the actual IF for a secondary endpoint depends on the final number of events observed

for that endpoint, which is inherently unknown at the interim analysis. This uncertainty complicates the application of fixed boundaries, as deviations from the assumed IF—due to over- or under-running—can lead to inflation or loss of the overall type I error rate control (Xu, Qin, & Wang, 2018).

To address this challenge, it is essential to adjust the significance level at the final analysis based on the actual IF for secondary endpoints. Such an adjustment ensures that the overall type I error rate remains controlled. In this context, we propose an alpha spending method in section 2 that adaptively modifies the significance level at the final analysis, accounting for the realized information fraction. Through simulation studies in section 3, we demonstrate that this approach effectively preserves the overall type I error rate, regardless of deviations in information time. As discussed in section 4, the method offers a practical and robust solution for secondary endpoint testing in complex clinical trial settings.

2. Methods

The rationale of alpha adjustment at FA is based on the fact that the log-rank test statistics at two different time points $Z(t_1), Z(t_2)$ asymptotically follow bivariate normal distribution with the correlation coefficient of $\sqrt{t_1/t_2}$ (Fleming & Harrington, 1991; Glimm, Maurer, & Bretz, 2010). Using the first secondary efficacy endpoint as an example, assuming the joint distribution changed with t_1 moving from 0.6 to 0.58 and t_2 remaining the same as 1. It became necessary to make an adjustment at the final analysis to uphold the overall alpha level with an unalterable alpha expenditure at t_1 . To be specific, we use $Z_P(0.6), Z_P(1)$ for log-rank test statistics with planned IF, and $Z_A(0.58), Z_A(1)$ for actual IF. The asymptotic distribution of $(Z_P(0.6), Z_P(1))$ under null hypothesis (i.e., hazard ratio is 1) is as below

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z_P(0.6) \\ Z_P(1) \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \sqrt{\frac{0.6}{1}} \\ \sqrt{\frac{0.6}{1}} & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right)$$

And OBF alpha spending function $\alpha_{OBF}(t)$ specifies alpha spent at IF=0.6 as 0.0076 and overall alpha is 0.05, that is, $\alpha_{OBF}(0.6) = 0.0076$ and $\alpha_{OBF}(1) = 0.05$. Assume the critical values for $Z_P(0.6), Z_P(1)$ are $b_P(0.6)$ and $b_P(1)$ respectively. That is

$$\begin{cases} P(|Z_P(0.6)| > b_P(0.6)) = \alpha_{OBF}(0.6) = 0.0076 \\ P(|Z_P(0.6)| > b_P(0.6) \text{ or } |Z_P(1)| > b_P(1)) = \alpha_{OBF}(1) = 0.05 \end{cases}$$

Considering that the same alpha 0.0076 is already spent on $Z_A(0.58)$ and $Z_A(0.58) \sim Z_P(0.6)$ under null hypothesis, the first equation above still applies to $Z_A(0.58)$ while the second equation above apparently doesn't apply to $(Z_A(0.58), Z_A(1))$ under null hypothesis as the joint distribution has changed. To control the overall type I error rate, we need to find a new critical value $b_A(1)$ for $Z_A(1)$ such that

$$P(|Z_A(0.58)| > b_P(0.6) \text{ or } |Z_A(1)| > b_A(1)) = 0.05$$

The equation has only one unknown parameter and can be treated as an integral equation with changing limits. This integral equation can be solved by some numerical methods. Alternatively, one useful approach involves the utilization of an alpha spending function, $\alpha(t) = \alpha t^\theta$ for $\theta > 0$, as discussed in DeMets & Lan (1994). By substituting the values of alpha spent at the interim analysis $\alpha(t)$, the true IF t , and the overall alpha level α into the equation, we can derive the value of the parameter. In the case of the secondary endpoint example, with α set at 0.05, t at 0.58, and

$\alpha(t)$ at 0.0076, we calculated a θ value of 3.45. Consequently, the final alpha level was adjusted downward from 0.0476 to 0.0474. I.e., $P(|Z_P(1)| > b_P(1)) = 0.0476$ and $P(|Z_A(1)| > b_A(1)) = 0.0474$.

3. Simulations

3.1. Simulation Settings

In the simulation, a total sample size of 9,500 were randomized into IP and control arms in a 1:1 ratio over a duration of 30 months with a lower enrollment rate at the beginning. The primary efficacy event is a specific CV event, the first secondary efficacy event has three components including the primary efficacy event, and the second efficacy event is the primary efficacy event in the first 120 days. We use P to represent the primary efficacy endpoint which is time from randomization to the first occurrence of the primary efficacy event, use S11 to denote the time from randomization to the first occurrence of the first component of the first secondary efficacy event, and so does S12. The event rates for P, S11, and S12 used for the simulation were exactly based on the event rate estimates summarized in [Table 1](#). In addition, we introduced a fabricated endpoint (labeled as “Extreme case”) deliberately designed with a quite different survival pattern compared to the real endpoints. This discrepancy was employed to markedly deviate its true information fraction at the interim analysis from the predefined threshold of 0.6 for the primary efficacy endpoint in the simulation.

The time to the first occurrence of the three distinct cardiovascular events, and additionally the fabricated endpoint, were individually and independently generated. The time to the first occurrence of the first and the second secondary endpoints were then calculated.

The number of iterations in this simulation was 10,000 for each scenario (explained in [3.2](#)). Within each iteration, the administration of treatment was concluded as soon as the count of patients experiencing the primary efficacy event reached 600.

[Table 1 Placebo Event Rates and Hazard Ratios]

	Month 1	Month 3	Year 1	Year 2	Hazard Ratios
P	3.00%	4.50%	6.00%	7.50%	0.75
S11	1.00%	2.90%	5.30%	7.10%	0.95
S12	0.17%	0.50%	1.10%	1.80%	0.88
Extreme Case			2.00%	25.00%	0.9

3.2. Simulation Results

Within the simulation, we examined two different scenarios. In the first scenario, we operated under the premise that treatment effects (as shown in [Table 1](#)) of IP over control exist for cardiovascular events to understand the true information fraction (IF) values that we may observe for the secondary efficacy endpoints. The results of the first scenario are presented in [Table 2](#). According to the simulation findings, the true IF value at the interim analysis stood at 0.54 for the first secondary efficacy endpoint and 0.79 for the second. Notably, the true IF value for the fabricated endpoint was 0.18. This remarkable difference from 0.6 should be attributed to the deliberately designed risk over time pattern.

Table 2 Average Number of Events Based on the Existence of Treatment Effects

	Primary	Secondary 1	Secondary 2	Extreme Case
IA	361	730	302	342
FA	600	1354	385	1925

True IF	0.6	0.54	0.79	0.18
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In the second scenario, we set the HR to 1, representing the absence of any treatment effects, across all cardiovascular events to assess the type I error rates. [Table 3](#) presents the true IF values at interim for the efficacy endpoints, which were found to be similar to those observed in the first scenario. This observation indicates that treatment effects have minimal influence on the true IF.

Table 3 Average Number of Events Based on HR=1

	Primary	Secondary 1	Secondary 2	Extreme Case
IA	361	690	305	288
FA	600	1235	438	1051
True IF	0.6	0.56	0.70	0.28

[Table 4](#) provides an overview of the overall type I error rates observed in the second scenario, while [Table 5](#) presents the type I error specifically at the interim analysis stage. It is worth mentioning that we employed the O'Brien-Fleming (OBF) boundary for all the endpoints. The alpha spent at IA and FA from OBF when IF=0.6 are 0.0076 and 0.0476 respectively. The type I error rates for all the endpoints at the interim analysis closely aligned with the planned values established as 0.0076 for the OBF boundary. With regards to the overall type I error rates, alpha adjustments at the final analysis were implemented with the true IF values to meticulously ensure overall type I error control.

The adjustments made to the overall type I error rates demonstrated minimal impact for the first and second secondary efficacy endpoints, primarily because the true IF values are close to 0.6. When a secondary endpoint's true IF much deviated from the IF for the primary endpoint, such as in the case of the fabricated endpoint, a more substantial adjustment was evident as displayed in [Table 4](#). Based on the simulation results, we anticipate that the overall type I error rates for all the secondary efficacy endpoints will remain controlled. The extent of adjustment necessitated by variations between the true IF and 0.6 is expected to be modest.

Table 4 Overall Type I Error

	Primary	Secondary 1	Secondary 2	Extreme Case
IF=0.6	0.0491	0.0526	0.0519	0.0528
True IF		0.0522	0.0525	0.0506

Table 5 Type I Error at the Interim Analysis

	Primary	Secondary 1	Secondary 2	Extreme Case
Planned Alpha Spent	0.0076	0.0076	0.0076	0.0076
Simulated	0.0074	0.0075	0.0073	0.0071

4. Conclusions

The differences between the true IF values and the benchmark value of 0.6 for the secondary efficacy endpoints are anticipated to be minimal regardless of the treatment effect sizes. This stability can be attributed to the similarity in risk over time patterns and the gradual recruitment of patients. The proposed alpha spending method, combined with the final alpha adjustment, is anticipated to effectively control the overall type I error rates for the secondary efficacy endpoints. Moreover, the extent of the final alpha adjustment is expected to be modest, ensuring a practical and reliable approach for maintaining statistical rigor in clinical trials.

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